

Refuting colonial narratives: Was Sri Rama non-vegetarian, a hunter and did he eat meat?

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Abstract

There has been a spate of mischievous attempts to tarnish the highest Hindutva icons of ancient Bharat Varsha. One of the common targets is Bhagavan Sri Rama who is portrayed as a hunter, consumer of meat and a non-vegetarian. This attempt at character assassination is typically done with a colonial agenda to denigrate Indian divinity, and prop up a monotheistic alternative. This topic has largely gone unnoticed by academics who rarely deal with real life issues of Hindutva. I examine the original Sanskrit textual evidence in the Valmiki Ramayana in meticulous detail to check the original intended meaning.

After evaluating the evidence, the inescapable conclusion is that Sri Rama lived like a complete ascetic, with no interest in the three activities of eating meat, hunting or killing animals. All attempts to denigrate Sri Rama is propped by deliberate mistranslations of Sanskrit words, malicious distortion of texts and a rampant ignorance of the highest (Paramarthika or Adhyathmika) meaning in the Itihasas. This exercise is a reminder that people with ill intent, malice and non-devout Hindus should be forbidden from reading or interpreting the Ramayana to suit their devious objectives.

Keywords: Ramayana, Sri Rama, Vegetarian, meat consumption, Adhyatma, Advaita, Ramayana interpretation

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1. Introduction

The interpretation of Ramayana has often bewildered modern historians. These are common questions: When was it written? What was the purpose? What is the message? Is it the story of a random king from a random province?

However, none of the academics have bothered to ask the practitioners, Ramayana Kathavachaks (story tellers) and priests, what the meaning of the Ramayana really is. Even the great poet Tulsidas noted that the true meaning of the Ramayana was not as a myth or story, but a description of Sri Rama as the highest reality (the highest Atman consciousness). All parts of the Ramayana are symbolic events connecting a person with the inner divinity within. Tulsidas Goswami was deeply influenced by the Adhyathma Ramayana, which posited every event in the Ramayana with a deep, symbolic meaning often unconnected to the event being described.

Missing this inner symbolic meaning, which the devout Hindus insist upon, the Western interpreters instead choose a literal objective translation, which is not how the original text is supposed to be read. With the incorrect perspective, they keep spreading a lot of disinformation about Indian texts. This again suits an imperialistic colonial agenda, which has remained in place right from the days of the British Raj.

2. Background

Here are the verses from the Valmiki Ramayana that are used to prove that Sri Rama never ate meat or hunted animals.

- 1) Ayodhya Kanda: 2.20.29, 2.34.59, 2.50.44, 2.54.16
- 2) Sundara Kanda: 5.48.16, 5.36.41

These are the verses that purportedly suggest that Rama hunted and ate meat.

- 1) Ayodhya Kanda: 2.52.102, 2.55.33, 2.56.21-28, 2.56.34, 2.96.1-2
- 2) Aranya Kanda: 3.43.20, 3.43.30, 3.44.27, 3.47.22-23, 3.68.32-33, 3.73.13-17

3. Arguments

Let us carefully analyse the verses that talk about Rama not being a hunter or a consumer of meat.

3.1) Arguments that Sri Rama stayed away from meat and hunting:

- 1) Shloka 2.20.29

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Sanskrit Verse:

चतुर्दश हि वर्षाणि वत्स्यामि विजने वने।
मधुमूलफलैर्जीवन्हित्वा मुनिवदामिषम्॥

Word by word translation:

Indeed (hi), (for) fourteen (chaturdasha) years (varshaani), (I shall) dwell (vathsyaami) in the solitary (vijane) forest (vane)

Living (jeevan) like (vath) a sage (muni) (with) honey (madhu), roots (moola) and fruits (phala), having abandoned (hithva) objects of worldly enjoyment (aamisham).

Commentary:

The verse is from Sri Rama to his mother, Kausalya. The shloka is self-explanatory. The only confusion being the word “aamisham” which means “steadfastness” and not “meat.” Only this meaning (of renouncement) flows as a natural consequence.

Even the English language has multiple symbolic representations. For example, if I say, “eat the meat of the fruit” or “eat the flesh of the fruit,” what does it mean? Any person with the slightest common sense will understand that the words “meat” and “flesh” used here are symbolic. They do not refer to “real meat” and “real flesh.” English is one of the great-grandchildren of Sanskrit. If the descendant can use symbolism, the ancestor can use symbolism a thousand times better.

2) Shloka 2.34.59

Sanskrit verse:

फलानि मूलानि च भक्षयन्वने
गिरींश्च पश्यन् सरितस्सरांसि च।
वनं प्रविश्यैव विचित्रपादपम्
सुखी भविष्यामि तवास्तु निर्वृतिः॥2.34.59॥

Word by word translation:

In the forest (vane) eating (bhakshyan) fruits (phalani) and roots (moolani), perceiving (pashyen) mountains (giri) and (cha) rivers (aaritha) and (cha) lakes (saraamsi)

Indeed (eva), having entered (pravishya) the forest (vanam) of varied (vichitra) trees (paadhapam), I shall be (bhavishyami) happy (sukhi), let that be (asthu) your (tava) satisfaction (nivriti).

Commentary:

The verse is from Sri Rama to his father, Dasharatha. Clearly, Sri Rama promises to eat only fruits and roots.

3) Shloka 2.50.44

Sanskrit verse:

कुशचीराजिनधरं फलमूलाशिनं च माम्।

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विद्धि प्रणिहितं धर्मे तापसं वनगोचरम् ॥

Word by word translation:

(Sri Rama): Wearing (dharam) Kusha (grass), garments of bark (cheera) and seated in the Paramatman (ajina), eating (aashinam) fruits (phalam) and (cha) roots (moola), I (maam) (exist).

Know (viddhi) (me) as concentrating (pranihitham) on Dharma (dharme) (as a) forest (vana) wandering (gaucharam) ascetic (taapasam).

Commentary:

The verse is from Sri Rama to Guha, head of the Nishadhas. The shloka is self-explanatory. The word “ajina” means black antelope skin. However, this is only a literal meaning. The symbolic meaning connects to the sacrifice, external universe, Vedas etc,

- As per the Krishna Yajur Veda 5.1.4, “*the black antelope skin is the sacrifice*” meaning that the black antelope skin has a symbolic meaning of a yagna where fire is worshipped. The word “tapas” in the original shloka means intense fire or meditation, and this resonates with black antelope which refers to the sacrificial fire.
- Krishna Yajur Veda 5.1.4 also notes that “*the black antelope skin is this (external universe).*” The external universe has to be sacrificed to know the Brahman. This is the inner meaning of offering one’s manifested form to the fire. The person has to give up the material body to know the Atman.
- Krishna Yajur Veda 6.1.3 states that “*The Rc and the Saman, unwilling to remain with the gods for the sacrifice, taking the form of a black antelope departed and remained away...This is the colour of the Rc, the white of the skin of the black antelope; the black is the colour of the Saman...The white of the black antelope skin is the colour of the day, the black of the night.*” This words shows that the black antelope has a deeply symbolic meaning of Rig and Sama Veda, of day and night etc. It is clear that black antelope refers to Rama indulging in the chant of the Rig and Sama Veda rather than wearing it around him as a garment.

The etymology of अजिन is अज् (unborn) + इन (that which). Ajina refers to the unborn supreme or the highest Atman. This, Ajina refers to the seat of the Atman. Note that the sacrifice, universe and the Vedas are all considered to be eternal as per Hindu thought. The next line talks of being an ascetic and tapasya. Hence, this interpretation is correct.

4) Shloka 2.54.16

Sanskrit verse:

पित्रा नियुक्ता भगवन् प्रवेक्ष्यामस्तपोवनम्।
धर्ममेव चरिष्याम स्तत्र मूलफलाशनाः ॥

Word by word translation:

O Lord (Bhagavan), commanded (niyuktha) by (my) father (pitra), I enter (pravekshaam) the forest (vana) of penance (tapo)

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Keeping my vow (charishyaam) of Dharma exclusively (eva), there (tatra) (we will) feed (aashna) on roots (moola) and phala (fruits).

Commentary:

These are words of Sri Rama to Rishi Bharadwaja. The shloka is self-explanatory. The key thing to note is that Sri Rama is living like a Brahmin ascetic and not like a warrior king. Hence, he is bound by self- imposed laws of Dharma of being a seeker of knowledge. That invokes him not killing other animals.

5) Shloka 5.48.16

Sanskrit verse:

तेन किं भ्रष्टराज्येन रामेण गतचेतसा।
करिष्यसि विशालाक्षि तापसेन तपस्विना॥

Word by word translation:

What (kim) (use) is that (thena) (one) fallen (bhrast) from his kingdom (raajyena)? With (ena) Rama, his intelligence (chetasa) is (long) gone (gatha)
O large eyed one (vishalakshi) (Sita), (what) will you do (karishyasi) with an ascetic (taapsena), the practitioner of intense tapas (tapasvina)

Commentary:

These are words from Ravana to Sita Devi. He tells Sita devi that Rama is no longer a king or a fighter in the forest. He is an intense ascetic always indulging in meditation. Clearly, these words of Ravana, Rama's greatest foe, proves that Sri Rama was incapable of hunting and killing animals, let alone cooking or eating their meat.

6) Shloka 5.36.41

Sanskrit verse:

न मांसं राघवो भुङ्क्ते न चाऽपि मधु सेवते।
वन्यं सुविहितं नित्यं भक्तमश्नाति पञ्चमम्॥

Word by word translation:

Sri Rama (Raghava) eats (bhunkte) not (na) the fleshy fruits (maamsam), nor (na) also (cha) even (api) cherish (sevathe) honey (madhu)
Daily (nithyam), in the forest (vanyam), eats (ashnathi) a fifth (panchamam) of the well prepared (suvihitham) boiled food (bhaktham).

Commentary:

These are words of Hanuman to Sita devi, who was trapped in Lanka. The words are similar to the earlier shlokas. We have seen fruits, roots and honey being used interchangeably in the previous shlokas. Hence, the word "maamsam" has to be interpreted carefully. It is used in Hindi and Malayalam even today to refer to the fleshy part of a fruit. It can also mean meat. The English word "flesh" also has two meanings – flesh of fruit and flesh of an animal. Hence, context is important. In this case, we have seen the words fruits,

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roots and honey being used as a combination and never alone. Hence, it is logical to assume that “maamsam” refers to fleshy part of a fruit.

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3.2) Arguments that Sri Rama may have consumed meat:

1) Shloka 2.52.102

Sanskrit verse:

तौ तत्र हत्वा चतुरो महामृगान्
वराहमृश्यं पृषतं महारुरुम्।
आदाय मेध्यं त्वरितं बुभुक्षितौ
वासाय काले ययतुर्वनस्पतिम्॥2.52.102॥

Word by word translation:

There (tatra), those two (thau) overcame (hathva) the four (chathuro) great (maha) seekings (mrighaan); avarice (varaaham), fear of death (rishyam), stains on character (prishtham) and great (maha) envy (ruram).

Having swiftly (tvaritham) taken (aadhaaya) the sacrificial offering (medhyam) because of a keen desire (bubhushitau) (for sacrifice); at that time (kale, they went (yayathu) to the sacrificial hall (vaasaaya) to the sacrificial post (vanaspathim)

Commentary:

This is the first night of Rama in the forests outside Ayodhya. He is in the region called Vatsa, the land of the young. There is a special significance to this first night outside the familiar region of Ayodhya. Sri Rama and his companions have to kill their inner demons to spend the rest of the 14 years in the forests. The killing of the big four refers to the killing of the big four for base desires.

There are two reasons why Mrigha has a symbolic meaning instead of the literal meaning of animals.

- 1) It makes no sense to kill four huge (maha) animals if the purpose was to eat them. When a pride of lions can be satisfied with one large deer for many days, why should three humans require four large animals as food for one night? Such an interpretation is nonsensical.
- 2) Nobody calls deer or wild boar as a huge animal. To call spotted deer as a great or huge animal defies common sense. For example, no villager, even today, thinks of spotted deer as anything but a weak and timid animal. Hence, the literal interpretation is incorrect.

Now let us look at the four great animals. The sacrifice of these animals means that evil thoughts have to be sacrificed on the altar of the yagna kund and good thoughts to be embraced. To think that real animals were sacrificed betrays a lack of understanding of the symbolic meaning of the Vedas.

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- 1) Varaha has the root word Vr which means to cover and to increase. In addition to wild boar, the word also means coin or money. Hence killing the animal Varaha is the symbolic of conquering avarice (the love for money).
- 2) Rishyam means death or a white footed antelope. One cannot be frightened of death in a jungle. The symbolic meaning is a better fit here even though an antelope is equally symbolic. The antelope signifies the knowledge of the Vedas. The capture of the white footed antelope signifies the conquest of the Shukla (white) Yajur Veda. I have already covered the Yajur Veda symbolism of antelopes with the Vedas for an earlier shloka.
- 3) Prishtham means spotted or dappled. By itself, it means a stain on one's character. However, when associated with an animal like the cow, it means the beginning of Atma Gyana. There are innumerable references to dappled cows in the Rig Veda.
- 4) The modern day meaning for Maha Ruru is great antelope. However, was that the original meaning? We have to look for other clues. Ruru also means dog. Bhagavatha Purana 5.26.11 says that the targets of envy manifest as Rurus to inflict punishment on envious people and that Rurus are crueller than a snake. Bhagavatha Purana 5.26.12 notes that Rurus torment people and eat their flesh. So clearly Ruru is a flesh-eating animal denoting envy, as per early Puranic interpretations.

Let us look at the other words:

- 1) Hathva can mean kill but also has a milder primary meaning called overcome. One overcomes their inner desires not one does not kill them.
- 2) Mrigha means not just animal. It also means pursuit, seeking, search, inquiry, hunting, investigation etc.
- 3) The original meaning of Medhyam was a sacrificial holy offering before it became known as food.
- 4) Bubishathau means keen desire and not hunger.
- 5) Vaasaaya means dwelling as well as sacrificial hall.
- 6) Vanispathim means forest as well as sacrificial post. This indicates a link to a fire ritual being performed.

It is not remarkable that every word in the second line has a link to a yagna sacrificial ritual. What is more appropriate? Is it that Sri Rama was hunting indiscriminately for food on his first night away from Ayodhya or conducting a ritual to mark an auspicious beginning to his time in the forests? Clearly the second choice makes the most sense. Hence, the first line should also flow with the same logic as the first line.

- 2) Shloka 2.55.33

Sanskrit verse:

क्रोशमात्रं ततो गत्वा भ्रातरौ रामलक्ष्मणौ।

बहून्मेध्यान्मृगान्हत्वा चेरतुर्यमुनावने॥2.55.33॥

Word by word translation:

Thereafter (tatha), the two brothers (bhraathrau), Rama and Lakshmana, having gone (gathva) only (maathram) about two miles (krosha),

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Many (bahuun) sacrificial offerings (medhyaan) (were offered) and (many) pursuits (mrighaan) were overcome (hathva) by wandering (cherathu) in the forests (vane) of (river) Yamuna.

Commentary:

Mrighaan means seeking or searching. Hence, the word mrighaan flows with the word medhyaam, as both are offerings to a sacrifice.

Yamuna means Durga, hence the meaning can also be that these sacrifices were offered before the eyes of Durga.

The word “cherathu” has the root word “char” that means to graze or wander. Many malicious interpreters interpret cherathu as “eat” which makes little etymological sense. Even today, no Hindi speaker will not confuse the word “charna” for eating.

3) Shloka 2.56.22

Sanskrit verse:

ऐणेयं मांसमाहृत्य शालां यक्ष्यामहे वयम्।

कर्तव्यं वास्तुशमनं सौमित्रे चिरजीविभिः।।2.56.22।।

Word by word translation:

In our abode (shaalam), we (vayam) shall offer oblations (yakshaamahe), the flesh of the fruits (maamsam) (essence of Vedas) to be offered (aahrtya) (is from) the Rig and Sama Vedas (eyneyem)

O Saumitri (Lakshmana), (it is) our duty (karthavyam) to consecrate (shamnam) the house (vaasthu), (blessed by) the long (chir) lived (jeevi) (ancestors).

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory. The flesh of the fruits refers to the essence of the Vedas.

ऐणेय or eyneyam means a black antelope or a doe eyed woman. Both are equivalent and is explained below:

- The black antelope refers to the Rig and Sama Veda. As per the Krishna Yajur Veda 6.1.3, “*This is the colour of the Rc, the white of the skin of the black antelope; the black is the colour of the Saman...*”
- The doe-eyed woman is a reference to Mahadevi (same as Shakti whom Sita devi represents). In Sundara Kanda 5.17.29, Sita devi is called मृगशाबनिभेक्षणाम् (that means eyes (eekshan) like (nibh) a young (shaab) animal (mrigha). The word एण specifically means the doe eyed woman, referring to Sita devi.

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Both interpretations are equally valid. I stick to the earlier translation because the second is not obvious to non-followers to Hindu Advaita. However, to help Advaitins understand, a question can be asked – why the reference to Mahadevi as Sita?

Answer: The Adhyatmik interpretation is that Sita devi is Maya or Prakriti. She is Mahadevi and no mere woman. Since all fruits come from trees that come from nature (Prakriti), Sita devi is said to be the mother of all trees and the mother of all fruits.

Finally, none of the references here are connected to consumption. All the references are to specific rites to be followed in Vedic yagna rituals. Shloka 2.56.29 calls Sri Rama knowledgeable in the chanting of Vedic mantras. Shloka 2.56.31 even names the various mantras chanted by Sri Rama and the deities the mantras address. Even word in the Ramayana has a Vedic connection.

4) Shloka 2.56.23

Sanskrit verse:

मृगं हत्वाऽऽनय क्षिप्रं लक्ष्मणेह शुभेक्षण।
कर्तव्यं शशास्त्रदृष्टो हि विधिर्धर्ममनुस्मर॥2.56.23॥

Word by word translation:

Lakshmana, the one with auspicious (shubhe) insights (akshana), overcome (hathva) the pursuit (mrigham) (of the material world), and bring (aanay) (the sacrificial offering) swiftly (shipram) here (iha)

(Our) duties (kartavya) are revealed (drishti) in the sacred scriptures (shaastraas), indeed Dharma is remembered (anusmara) in the sacred rites (vidhi).

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory. We have already seen that mrigha refers to pursuit and not to killing. The Vedic rituals are completely symbolic, and the rituals observed without symbolism are meaningless actions.

5) Shloka 2.56.25

Sanskrit verse:

ऐणेयं श्रपयस्वैतच्छालां यक्ष्यामहे वयम्।
त्वर सौम्य मुहूर्तोऽयं ध्रुवश्च दिवसोऽप्ययम्॥2.56.25॥

Word by word translation:

We (vayam) shall prepare for sacrifice (shrapayasya) (and) offer to the sacrifice (yakshaamahe) these (etath) Rig and Sama Vedas (eyneyem)

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Hurry (tvara), O gentle one (soumya) (Lakshmana), this (ayam) auspicious time (muhurtha) and (cha) this (ayam) day (dhivas) is also (api) fixed (dhruva).

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory. We have argued earlier that ऐणेयं means black antelope that represents the Rig and Sama Vedas, or the doe-eyed woman, who is Sri Mahadevi. In the first case, Sri Rama chants the Rig and Samsa Vedas. In the second case, Sri Rama prays to the mother of the universe, Mahadevi Shakti. There are no contradictions between both interpretations. Both flows into the other. In a yagna, this is what one is exactly supposed to perform.

The word, shrapayasya is interpreted as cook, but it also means prepare for yagna. Once we pick up the yagna sacrifice as the common theme, every word now begins to make sense. Yagnas have to done at a specific auspicious time, a practice followed by all Hindus to this day.

6) Shloka 2.56.26

Sanskrit verse:

स लक्ष्मणः कृष्णमृगं मेध्यं हत्वा प्रतापवान्।
अथ चिक्षेप सौमित्रिस्समिद्धे जातवेदसि॥2.56.26॥

Word by word translation:

He (sa), the mighty (prathapvaan) Lakshmana finished (hathva) the Rig and Sama Vedas (krishnamrigham) as a sacrificial offering (medhyam)

Then (atha), Saumitri (Lakshmana) cast (chikshep) (the sacrificial offering) and kindled (samiddha) the sacrificial fire (jathavedas).

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory.

Hathva means finish as well as to kill. Even in English today, the words “finish him” may also mean “kill him.” However, finish also has different meanings.

The Krishna Mrigham stands for black antelope. It is a symbolic meaning referring to the Rig and Sama Vedas. As noted earlier, the black antelope has a completely symbolic meaning as per the Krishna Yajur Veda 6.1.3.

7) Shloka 2.56.27

Sanskrit verse:

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तन्तु पक्वं परिज्ञाय निष्टप्तं छिन्नशोणितम्।
लक्ष्मणः पुरुषव्याघ्रमथ राघवमब्रवीत्॥2.56.27॥

Word by word translation:

Having perceived (parigyaay) by complete (ni) meditation (tapas) on the division (chinna) of the perfect (pakvam) Paramatman (tanthu) into the nourisher of life (shonitha) (Prakriti)

Lakshmana, the tiger (vyaagram) among men (purush), then addressed (abraveeth) Raghava (Sri Rama)

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory.

In Bhagavatha Purana 8.16.31, तन्तु or tanthu is defined as the Atman.

The word निष्टप्त is broken as नि + तप्त. The root word of तप्त is तप् which means heat of Tapasya.

Shonitha has various meanings including nourisher of life, life, blood etc. The division of Brahman into Maya or Prakriti is mentioned here. In Ayurveda, Shonitha means Prakrithi. Hence, we are reassured that this interpretation is absolutely correct.

8) Shloka 2.56.28

Sanskrit verse:

अयं सर्वः समस्ताङ्गः श्रुतः कृष्णमृगो मया।
देवतां देवसङ्काश यजस्व कुशलो ह्यसि॥2.56.28॥

Word by word translation:

This (ayam) entire (sarva) Rig and Sama Vedas (krishnamrgha) with all (samastha) the parts (anga) has been sacrificially offered (shrith) by me (mayaa).

Indeed (hi), you (Rama) are (asi) a Deva (devathaam); similar (sangkaaksha) to a Deva, perform a yagna (yajasva) auspiciously (kushalo).

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory.

Lakshmana finishes his recitation and passes on the yagna rituals to Sri Rama, who is clearly identified as a Deva in this shloka. For people who do not understand Vedic or Hindu symbolism, their interpretation is that Lakshmana was cooking

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The word श्रुतः has the root word शृ that refers to a sacrificial pouring or offering.

Krishnamrgha refers to the Rig and Sama Vedas. Krishna Yajur Veda 6.1.3 defines the symbolic meaning of the black antelope.

For people who do not understand symbolism, they interpret the shloka as Lakshmana cooking a black antelope with all its limbs inside a pot right before a yagna. One person trying to cook an entire antelope by himself right before a yagna is an absurd interpretation. Is it possible to cook an entire animal right before a yagna? Is it possible to cook an antelope in a pot single handedly? Such an interpretation lacks an trace of mental judgement.

9) Shloka 2.56.34-35

Sanskrit verse:

वन्यैर्माल्यैः फलैर्मूलैः पक्वैर्मसैर्यथाविधि ।

अद्भिर्जपैश्च वेदोक्तैर्दार्भैश्च ससमित्कुशैः ॥2.56.34॥

तौ तर्पयित्वा भूतानि राघवौ सह सीतया ।

तदा विविशतु शशालां सुशुभां शुभलक्षणौ ॥2.56.35॥

Word by word translation:

According to (yatha) (Vedic) rules (vidhi), with forest (vanyai) (produce), garlands (maalyai) (of flowers), with fruits (phalai), with roots (moolyai), with perfect (pakvai) (incantations), with meat of fruits (maamsai),

(They) chanted mantras (japai) as mentioned in the Vedas (vedhokthai) with (offerings) of water (abdi) and (cha) darbha (grass) and (cha) samit (twigs) with (sa) kusha (grass). 2.56.34

These two (tau), descendants of Raghu (Raghavau) (Rama and Lakshmana) together with (sa) Sita (Sithya), having satisfied (tarpayithva) the (divine) beings (bhutani)

Then (tadha) (they) entered (vivishathu) the good (su), auspicious (shubh) shashaalam (dwelling) (full of) propitious (shubh) signs (lakshnau). 2.56.35

Commentary:

The meaning is self-explanatory.

The words pakvai and maamsai are both independent and have no connection. The suffix for all words in the first line is vai, meaning with. The perfection (pakvai) refers to perfect chanting of the Vedas. Shloka 2.56.31 refers to shlokas addressed to Vishvadevas, Rudra and Vishnu. Hence, this interpretation has complete support and is consistent. The word “maamsai” refers to meat of fruits.

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10) Shloka 2.96.1

Sanskrit verse:

तां तथा दर्शयित्वा तु मैथिलीं गिरिनिम्नगाम्।
निषसाद गिरिप्रस्थे सीतां मांसेन छन्दयन्॥2.96.1॥

Word by word translation:

Thus (tatha), having shown (darshyitva) her (taam), Maithili (Sita devi), the descending river (nimngaa) on the mountain (giri), then (tu)

Sitting down (nishsaadh) (on the) mountain (giri) peak (prasthe), delighting (chandyan) Sita (with) fleshy fruits (maamsen).

Commentary:

The shloka is self-explanatory. It is not clear how one meat can pop from nowhere on a mountain peak. However, three shlokas earlier, in shloka 2.95.17, it is mentioned that Rama bathes three times a day and eats मधुमूलफलाशनः (edible honey, roots and fruits). Hence the word maamsen has to refer to fruits.

11) Shloka 2.96.2

Sanskrit verse:

इदं मेध्यमिदं स्वादु निष्टप्तमिदमग्निना।
एवमास्ते स धर्मात्मा सीतया सह राघवः॥2.96.2॥

Word by word translation:

This (idam) sacrificial offering (medhyam), this (idam) charm (swadhu), this (idam) heated (nihtapth) by fire (agnina)

Thus (evam). Dharma and the Atman (Dharmatma) remained (aasthe) with Sita (seethya) together (saha) with he (sa), Raghava (Rama).

Commentary:

In the middle of a peak, where is fire? There is no talk of lighting a fire on the peak. Hence, the conclusion is that Rama is referring to the charm of Mount Chitrakuta being a result of a sacrifice made in the past. When the symbol of the yagna (sacrifice) is invoked, then the word Agni (fire) gets new meaning. Shloka 2.95.6 talks of rishis with matted locks

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and deer skins offering morning ablutions. Shloka 2.95.7 discusses how Munis of rigid austerities worship Aditya (the Sun). Shloka 2.95.13 (six shlokas earlier) discusses how Siddhas endowed with asceticism, self-restraint and tranquillity are cleansed of impurities in the waters. The sacrificial interpretation flows with the devotion mentioned explicitly in these earlier shlokas. The hunter interpretation is forced, out of context and an aberration.

12) Shloka 3.43.18

Sanskrit verse:

जीवन्न यदि तेऽभ्येति ग्रहणं मृगसत्तमः।

अजिनं नरशार्दूल रुचिरं मे भविष्यति॥3.43.18॥

Word by word translation:

With they (te) (Rama and Lakshmana) approaching (abhyethi) the excellent (satthatham) hunt (mrigha); if (yadhi) (the golden Rakshasa) is captured (grihanam) dead [not (na) alive (jeevan)],

Seated in the Paramatman (ajinam), the brilliance (ruchiram) of the male (nara) Rakshasa (shaardhul) shall become (bhavishyathi) mine (me).

Commentary:

The shloka is self-explanatory. The skins of elephants, tigers and lions are used as a seat in yagnas in the same way as black antelope skin.

Shaardhul has two meanings, a tiger as well as a rakshasa. There is a pun intended here by Valmiki. The deer looks like a tiger as well as a Rakshasa. It is incorrect to interpret narashardul as a reference to Rama as lion among men. The reason is that the word “te” used in the first line is not singular, however the reference to narashardul is in singular, so the reference “te” cannot be to Rama. The subject has to be different in both cases. The first line refers to Rama and Lakshmana, and the second line refers to the golden deer. The word Rakshasa is used multiple times in the chapter. The word vyaagra is used to refer to tiger two other times in the chapter, so the use of Shaardul is notable.

While the second line of 3.43.18 may look out of place, a look at the second line of 3.43.19 reveals that this interpretation of “ajina” as contemplation on the Atman is completely correct. Shloka 3.43.19 talks of Sita devi being seated on grass to offer divine worship.

13) Shloka 3.43.19

Sanskrit verse:

निहतस्यास्य सत्त्वस्य जाम्बूनदमयत्वचि।

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शष्पबृस्यां विनीतायामिच्छाम्यहमुपासितुम्॥3.43.19॥

Word by word translation:

Of this (asya) slain (nihathasya), that possesses (mayya) the excellent (sathvasya) golden (jaambunadh) skin (tvach)

In a seat (brsyaam) of fresh grass (shashpa), I (aham) humbly (vineethayaam) desire (icchami) to worship (supaasith)

Commentary:

The shloka is self-explanatory. Sita devi talks of the Rakshasa that possessor of the golden skin and how it needs to be slain. She does not discuss about Sri Rama brining the skin with him. While the second line talks of being seated and offering worship, it never says that the animal skin is used to as a seat for worship.

Interpretations that suggest that the animal was killed for meat or for the skin is a fanciful and unwarranted extrapolation not supported by the literal text of the Ramayana.

14) Shloka 3.43.20

Sanskrit verse:

कामवृत्तमिदं रौद्रं स्त्रीणामसदृशं मतम्।

वपुषा त्वस्य सत्त्वस्य विस्मयो जनितो मम॥3.43.20॥

Word by word translation:

In my belief (matham), this (idam) feminine (sthreenaam) universal destruction (raudram) (of evil) is unlike desire (kaama) driven (vritham) (actions)

Your (tvasya) beauty (vapusha) and Sattvik excellence (sattvasya) produces (janithau) amazement (vismayo) in me (mam)

Commentary:

There is an intense argument on who is the object of Rama's description. Most verses interpret the beauty as belonging to the golden deer. However, there are reasons why I think that approach is incorrect.

- 1) Raudram is a description of Rudra, the form of Shiva who acts as the universal destroyer. It is a completely incongruous word to use for a deer hunt. However, if interpreted as the symbolic destruction of universal evil (that the deer represents), the reference to Rudra and Shiva makes sense.

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- 2) There is nothing Sattvik about the deer. There is everything Sattvik about Sita devi. Hence, the term Sattvik reference is to Sita devi instead of the golden deer.
3) The amazement is because of Sita's need to worship by herself. That act of worship is a Sattvic act, that Sri Rama commends.

15) Shloka 3.43.21

Sanskrit verse:

तेन काञ्चनवर्णेन मणिप्रवरशृङ्गिणा।

तरुणादित्यवर्णेन नक्षत्रपथवर्चसा॥3.43.21॥

Word by word translation:

By that (thena) golden (kaanchen) color (varna), excellent (pravar) jeweled (mani) mountain peak (shringa)

(With the) color (varna) of the young (taruna) (rising) sun (Aditya), the lustrous (varchsa) path (patha) of the stars (nakshatra) (beckons)

Commentary:

Who is speaking these words? Everyone assumes it is Sri Rama. However, the second line of 3.43.22 states that it is Sita devi speaking these words (एवं सीतावचः श्रुत्वा)

This is important because Sita devi is describing the state of worship and supreme bliss attained from the yagna she was going to offer on fresh grass (3.43.19)

The word "shringa" has different meanings – horns as well as a mountain peak The word is equally applicable to meditation as well as to a hunt.

16) Shloka 3.43.30

Sanskrit verse:

मांसहेतोरपि मृगान्विनोदार्थं च धन्वनः।

घ्नन्ति लक्ष्मण राजानो मृगयायां महावने॥3.43.30॥

Word by word translation:

Also (api), for the motive (hethu) of meat (maamsa) and (cha) for the object (artham) of amusement (vinodh), the animals (mrigaan) are (the constellation Dhanu) (dhanvan)

O Lakshmana, in the hunt (mrgyaayaam), (the rakshasaas) kill (gnanthi) kings (rajaano) in the great (mahaa) forest (vana) (of Samsara)

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Commentary:

Sri Rama warns Lakshmana that the Rakshasas who pose as deer represents the evil of the world. These rakshasas kill kings for amusement and for their flesh. The reference is not to Lakshmana killing the deer, but the evil Rakshasas killing good people. Shloka 3.43.37 makes it clear that Rama and Lakshmana both knew that the golden deer was a Rakshasa in disguise.

This is the only meaning that emerges when each line is interpreted separately. Malicious interpreters mix words across lines to make it look as if Lakshmana hunts for amusement when the right interpretation is that Rakshasas kill for amusement.

Dhanvan refers to Sagittarius or Dhanu rashi which is symbolized by the hunter. The Rakshasas are always waiting to kill good and pious people. This symbolically means that evil is waiting to overpower the mind of good and pious people any moment. This interpretation ties with 3.43.32 where Rama talks of the planet Shukra or Venus. The reference is always to the planets and constellations.

Rajaano is a plural word that refers to kings.

Mrga refers to both the prey and the hunt.

The great forest refers to Samsara.

17) Shloka 3.44.27

Sanskrit verse:

निहत्य पृषतं चान्यं मांसमादाय राघवः।

त्वरमाणो जनस्थानं ससाराभिमुखस्तदा॥3.44.27॥

Word by word translation:

And (cha) having slain (nihathya) another (anyam) spotted (prishtham) (stain of the mind), Raghava (Sri Rama) grabbed (aadya) the essence (maamsam) (of Karma Yoga)

Then (tadha), (Sri Rama) hurrying (tvarmaano) proceeded (sasaar) facing (mukha) towards (abhi) the land (sthana) of people (jana).

Commentary:

In 3.44.26, the words “राक्षसं मृगरूपं तं हत्वा” mention clearly that Sri Rama killed the Rakshasa in the form of a deer. After killing the golden deer after Sita devi requested it, why would he kill one more deer. Nobody asked for one more deer.

3.44.25 also states that Maaricha screamed the words, O Lakshmana, O Rama to make it appear that Sri Rama was injured. Sri Rama was filled with fear and apprehension on hearing these words. Would not a sane person immediately rush back to their home when

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they finish their task and are filled with foreboding. Would they dither to kill one more deer? Nothing about the interpretation of killing another deer makes any sense.

However, if read symbolically, the references make sense. The word “prishtham” just means “spots,” it does not mean “spotted deer.” After killing the evil that Maaricha represented, Sri Rama cleansed his mind. Such an interpretation is perfectly logical.

The question arises, what is the reference to “maamsam?” It is the meat or tasty interior of an action. In this case, it is the fruits of Sri Rama’s virtuous action – of killing a Rakshasa. This virtuous action is Karma Yoga.

The word “jana sthana” is also strange language. Did Sri Rama leave the land of mortals and is that why he comes back to the world of people? Literally, the choice of words makes no sense unless interpreted symbolically. Sri Rama slayed the Rakshasa of his mind in deep meditation and then attained bliss in his mind. He had to shake himself away from the reverie of his meditation and come back to the world of mortals which he was inhabiting. The killing of Maaricha was a pure meditative exercise, and it is not to be taken literally.

There are no golden deer or deer with gems in their horns. These allegories are but reflections of spiritual impediments. Killing them is a symbolic indication of spiritual progress.

18) Shloka 3.47.22-23

Sanskrit verse:

समाश्वस मुहूर्तं तु शक्यं वस्तुमिह त्वया ॥3.47.22॥

आगमिष्यति मे भर्ता वन्यमादाय पुष्कलम्।

रुरून्गोधा न्वराहांश्च हत्वाऽदायाऽमिषान्बहून् ॥3.47.23॥

Word by word translation:

Compose yourself (samakshvasa), (O Ravana) for 48 minutes (muhurtham), then (tu) it will be possible (shakyam) for you (tvaya) to dwell (vasthum) here (iha).

My (me) husband (bhartha) (Rama) will come (aagamishyathi) from the forest (vanyam) having obtained (aadhaaya) (yogic) excellence (pushkalam) (after),

having slain (hathva) envy (ruru), stubbornness (godha), avarice (varaha) and having taken (aadhaaya) the many (bahuun) baits of the flesh (aamishaan)

Commentary:

Ruru refers to deer but also symbolizes envy. Varaha refers to money and avarice, as we have seen earlier. Godha refers to the monitor lizard, which is well known for its stubborn nature.

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Aamishan refers not only to food, but to the pleasures of the world, and to the baits of the world of Samsara.

19) Shloka 3.68.32

Sanskrit verse:

रामोऽथ सहसौमित्रिर्वनं गत्वा स वीर्यवान्॥3.68.32॥

स्थूलान्हत्वा महारोहीननुतस्तार तं द्विजम्।

Word by word translation:

Then (atha), Rama along with Lakshmana (Saumitri) departed (gathva) to the forest (vanam) he (sa) in a state of (vaan) of heroic power (veerya)

Having overcome (hathva) the strong (sthula) and huge (maha) red doe (roheen) (restless mind), later (anu) (the offering) was spread (tasthaar) to him (tham), the twice born (dvijham) (Jatayu).

Commentary:

Jatayu never asked for any offering. Why would Rama then give Jatayu a red deer as an offering? A better explanation is that Sri Rama stilled his restless mind and his emotions, before offering the funeral rites for Jatayu.

Roheen means a red doe and a restless mind.

Neither Sri Rama nor Jatayu were Brahmins. Sri Rama was a Kshatriya and Jatayu was a bird. Even Hanuman is described as a Janeudari Brahmin. The fact that Jatayu is referred to as a Brahmin means that character defined a Brahmin in the past, not form, appearance or birth.

20) Shloka 3.68.33

Sanskrit verse:

रोहिमांसानि चोत्कृत्य पेशीकृत्य महायशाः॥3.68.33॥

शकुनाय ददौ रामो रम्ये हरितशाद्वले।

Word by word translation:

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The meat (maamsa) around the seed (rohi) was cut (utkarya) and (cha) the fruit peel (pesha) was properly acted on (kritya) (removed) by the great (maha) yasha (one of fame) (Sri Rama)

To the bird of prey (shakun) (Jatayu), Rama gave (dadau) delightful (ramye) green (harith) fresh grass (shaadvale)

Commentary:

Why would meat be offered to a Brahmin, the twice-born Jatayu? Offerings of meat made to a Brahmin as part of funeral rites is utter blasphemy and makes absolutely no sense.

Secondly, the second line states explicitly that Rama offered green fresh grass to Jatayu.

How then is it possible to justify Rama offering meat to Jatayu? Clearly the answer has to be found in symbolism.

The word “pesha” holds the key. It means both a ball of flesh and a fruit peel.

Rohi means a seed as well as a kind of deer. Now, we have to choose the interpretation that resonates with the second line. Since the second line has no mention of meat and conversely suggests the grass was the only offering, we have to interpret the first line as Rama removing the peels and meat of the fruit. We have seen earlier that Rama always offered fruits before important yagna rituals. Hence this interpretation makes the most sense.

The reference to the fruit has deeper Adhyatma undertones. The fruit refers to the fruit of the steady mind that is no longer restless. The seed is the ego (Ahamkara) which is hard to crack. The rind refers to the body. Once the yogi surpasses the body and overcomes the ego, he is left with a high level of Atma Gyana.

21) Shloka 3.73.13

Sanskrit verse:

नोद्विजन्ते नरान्दृष्ट्वा वधस्याकोविदाश्शुभाः॥3.73.13॥

घृतपिण्डोपमान् स्थूलास्तान्द्विजान्भक्षयिष्यथः।

Word by word translation:

(The birds of Pampa) do not (na) tremble (udhvijante) on seeing (drishtva) men (naraan), the auspicious (shubaaha) (birds) will destroy (vadh) ignorance (akovida)

In comparison to (upmaan) offerings of liquid ghee (ghrtha) and offerings of solid butter (pinda), those (thaan) you both shall consume (bhakshayikshayatha), O powerful (sthuulaan) twice-borns (dvijaan) (Brahmins)

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Commentary:

The reference to ghrtha and pinda is a reminder that every reference to killing or overcoming in the Ramayana is always accompanied by a reference to a yagna. Interpreters need to ask why this is the case? The only way to reconcile the yagna and the actions surrounding it is to recognize that these actions are intimately tied to the yagna, and have deeply symbolic meaning.

The words वधस्याकोविदाश्शुभाः is like a popular adage or proverb. The words are esoteric and there is no need to connect those words to the situation being described. Introducing proverbs into regular speech abruptly, is a common feature of all Indian languages even today.

There is no reference to Rama or Lakshmana killing or eating birds, unless the words of first and second lines are mixed haphazardly and the meanings twisted. The birds seem to be called “Shubha” or auspicious.

The second line makes it explicit that Rama and Lakshmana have to consume butter and ghee, the sacrificial offerings. This is in recognition of their divine status as Vishnu and Adishesha. The goal of the yagna is to realize Vishnu, the Paramatman. There is no even a hint in either of the two lines that Rama and Lakshmana would kill the birds, let alone consume them.

Even though Rama and Lakshmana are Kshatriyas, they are called Brahmins. This is one more example that in the Vedic past, the Brahmin caste was decided by actions rather than by birth. Caste by birth is a modern abomination.

The meaning of this shlokas is not as tight knit as in other shlokas. However, the interpreter should desist from adding more detail than is present in the shloka. The interpretation should be strictly on the basis of words from the text and not words introduced from outside.

22) Shloka 3.73.14

Sanskrit verse:

रोहितान्वक्रतुण्डांश्च नडमीनांश्च राघव।।3.73.14।।

पम्पायामिषुभिर्मत्स्यांस्तत्र राम वरान्हतान्।

Word by word translation:

The reddish one (Rohitha) (the restless mind) is (ruled by) the bent (vakra) trunks (thundaam) (Lord Ganesha) and (cha) the impervious (nada) fishes (meenaam) (is ruled by) by Rama (Raghava)

There (tatra), in the Pampa (pampaayaam) (waters), the fishes (matsyaan) (seek) blessings (varaan) from Rama, (to have worries) slain (hathan) by his arrows (ishubhi)

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Commentary:

वरान्हतान् is a pun that means blessing + destroyer as well as excellent destroyer.

तुण्डान् is plural accusative. The bent trunks refer to the panchamukhi (five faced) form of Ganesha.

The impervious fishes refer to the stubborn humans who refuse to accept Atma Gyana.

The keys to unlocking this shloka are the words “vakra thunda” and “varaan.” It is absurd to think of a fish with a twisted trunk. Vakra thunda is a reverent prayer to Lord Ganesha, the lord of auspicious beginnings.

Similarly, “varaan” has multiple meanings like blessing, a dissolute person as well as excellence. Hence, another possible interpretation is that self-control can be obtained by seeking Sri Rama’s blessings.

Interpreting the shloka as Rama killing the hapless fishes is a blatant distortion of the devotional and ascetic nature of Sri Rama in the Ramayana. Any violence in this shloka is out of touch with all the succeeding shlokas which suggest extreme tranquillity and peace. Interpreters should place the interpretations in consonance with the rest of the chapter, and not make the distortions in the shlokas stand out conspicuously.

Interpretations should play close heed to how the devout have interpreted the same texts over millennia. Every other factor being equal, the devout interpretation should be preferred over the malicious and mudslinging interpretations.

23) Shloka 3.73.15

Sanskrit verse:

निस्त्वक्पक्षानयस्तप्तानकृशानेककण्टकान्॥3.73.15॥

तव भक्त्या समायुक्तो लक्ष्मणस्सम्प्रदास्यति।

Word by word translation:

Without (ni) coverings (tvak) on the sides (paksha) (of the body), scorched (tapta) by the fires (ayas) (of tapasya), the emaciated one (krishaan), (the one) with one (eka) enemy (akantakhaan) (Tamas),

Lakshmana, completely (sam) immersed (yuktho) with Bhakti (bhakthya), will deliver (pradhasyethi) entirely (sam) for you (tava) (Rama).

Commentary:

The first line is a description of Lakshmana. He barely has coverings on his body, is full of austerity, is weak and looks emaciated. However, he is still a complete enemy of Tamasic destructive forces. He was the first to spot the devilish trick played by Maricha in the form

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of the golden deer. Other Ramayana accounts talk of Lakshmana having not slept for 14 years in order to protect Sita and Rama. His austerities knew no bounds.

Some interpreters talk of prawns being baking on iron skewers etc. This is utter nonsense. In this shloka there is absolutely no reference to fishes. There is but one object, which is Lakshmana. If one knew the nature of Lakshmana, one would know that the extreme ascetic description perfectly applied to him.

When it comes to textual exegesis, the word

निस्त्वक्पक्षानयस्तप्तानकृशानेककण्टकान् means नि-त्वक्-पक्षान् + अयस्-तप्तान् + कृशान् + एक-कण्टकान्

कण्टकान् means thorns but also means enemies. कण्टकम् means thorn on society or an evil person

24) Shloka 3.73.16

Sanskrit verse:

भृशते खादतो मत्स्यान्पम्पायाः पुष्पसञ्चये ॥3.73.16॥

पद्मगन्धि शिवं वारि सुखशीतमनामयम्।

Word by word translation:

The fishes (matysaan) of (river) Pampa (pampayaa) were eating (kaadhato) an superlative (brishyate) abundance (sangchaye) of flowers (pushpa)

The lotuses (padma) were fragrant (gandhi) and auspicious (shivam), the waters (vari) were pleasantly (sukh) cool (sheetham) and free of illness (anaamayam) (pure)

Commentary:

In this shloka, there is no indication that the reference is to Rama or Lakshmana. They are not even mentioned in this shloka. The fishes are the only living beings mentioned here outside the flowers and lotuses. Hence, interpreters to assume that the shloka reference is to Rama eating fishes has no basis. Such an interpretation is unfounded on fact and borne from pure malice.

Any other interpretation also runs into many problems. Whom does the word “brishyate” refer to?

25) Shloka 3.73.17

Sanskrit verse:

उद्धृत्य सतताक्लिष्टं रौप्यस्फाटिकसन्निभम् ॥3.73.17॥

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असौ पुष्करपर्णेन लक्ष्मणः पाययिष्यति।

Word by word translation:

Having drawn out water (udhhrith), which is eternally (sathatha) aklishtam (untainted), resembling (sannibham) silvery (raupyam) crystal (sphatikam)

With a (ena) lotus (pushkar) leaf (parna) there (asau), Lakshmana will offer water to drink (paayayishyathi).

Commentary:

After a discussion of the waters in the earlier shloka, this shloka discusses what Rama and Lakshmana intended to do with the waters. Lakshmana is there to offer the tranquil waters to others, not to kill birds or cause destruction. Such behaviour is uncharacteristic of the ascetic lifestyles that Rama and Lakshmana were leading. Hence, implausible interpretations are blatantly wrong.

4. Discussion

There are two issues that any interpreter will face with trying to understand the Ramayana from the perspective of Sri Rama being a hunter.

- 1) Any discussion of the past is difficult, because the author is no longer around. Hence, the rules to follow when interpreting the past are consistency of the hypothesis intra-text, consistency of hypothesis across texts, and how traditional devotees interpret the text. Only if the three criteria are fulfilled, can any hypothesis be taken seriously. The problem occurs when anyone enters the field without establishing any ground rules and talks whatever nonsense they want. Treating Sri Rama as the Paramatman is in concordance with the way devotees perceive Hindutva, drives consistency across the Ramayana and also reinforces the single unity among all Hindu Shastras.
- 2) There are shlokas suggesting that he did not eat meat, and some purportedly suggesting he did. Either the text is contradictory or is consistent. If the text is consistent, then all the shlokas should be explainable with one perspective. I had tried to do so by showing that the “hunter” explanation is full of incoherence, without context, unfamiliar with Sanskrit lexicon, and an utter failure to understand Vedic symbolism. I challenge such interpreters to argue otherwise, and find similar gaps with my interpretation.
- 3) Every shloka that talks about “hunting” or consuming “meat” is followed immediately by a Vedic sacrificial yagna. Is that mere coincidence or a fatal misunderstanding of Vedic symbolism?

5. Conclusion

It is clear that Sri Rama is a vegetarian, non-hunter and never consumed meat. This is no contradiction in the Valmiki Ramayana, the oldest and most well-known Ramayana. Keeping the debate on mistranslations of Sanskrit words and improper knowledge of Adhyatma interpretations aside, there is another larger question – how does one makes sense of a text that belongs to another yuga (cycle of creation)? Is it wise to extend the objective reality of this world and yuga to study the context of another reality situated in another yuga. Is a direct one-to-one comparison meaningful or even sensible?

Secondly, interpreters of the Ramayana have to make up their mind to whether the Ramayana is to be read literally with an objective meaning or instead symbolically with an Adhyathmik meaning. For example, one cannot say that the Rama Sethu, Pushpaka Vimana and Brahmastras are devoid of objective meaning and then insist that the mistranslated verses of Rama eating meat is filled with objective meaning. One cannot argue that texts cannot be read literally in one instance and should be read literally in another instance. This points to a schizoid approach among Indologists today.

If the Indologists are intellectually honest, they should either take all the verses seriously or treat all the verses as symbolic. The Adhyathmik interpretation neatly sidesteps these blunders by stating that the Ramayana is completely symbolic. Every verse has to be interpreted for its inner symbolic meaning. Hence, Adhyathmik interpretations, whether in a pure Bhakti (devotional) or Advaita (intellectual), is the right way to read the Ramayana. The seeming inconsistencies of the Ramayana can be reconciled by using the approach of Adhyathma. The inconsistencies are not to be found in the Ramayana verses, but manifest in the minds of ignorant interpreters who use the wrong tools to interpret the Sacred texts of Hindutva.

6. Acknowledgments

IIT Kanpur Ramayana website for English translations: <https://www.valmiki.iitk.ac.in/>

7. References